

ZAHIRIDDIN MUHAMMAD BABUR DYNASTY'S MILITARY ARTISTRY

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Abstract: This article describes the Babur princes, their military system, as well as the composition of the army.

Key words: Army, march, soldier, king, prince, servant, state, official, commander.

Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur was born on February 14, 1483 in Andijan in the family of Sultan Umarshaikh Mirza, the ruler of the Fergana estate, the fifth generation of the master Amir Temur. Babur Mirza's mother Qutlugh Nigor Khanim was the daughter of Tashkent Khan Yunus Khan, who was considered the 15th generation of Genghis Khan. Umarshaikh Mirza had three sons and five daughters from his five wives. Khonzada Begum (1478) and Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur Mirza were born to Khanim Kutlugh Nigor. Jakhongir Mirza (1485) was born to his Mongolian wife Fatima Sultan Begum, and Mehribonu Begim (1478), Nasir Mirza (1487) and Shahribonu Begim (1491) were born to Umid Agacha from Andijan. Yodgor Sultan Begim (1494) was born to Agha Sultan Begim and Rukiya Sultan Begim (1494) to Sultan Mohim's concubine.

According to historical sources, Baburshah had four sons: Muhammad Humayun Mirza, Kamran Mirza, Khindol Mirza and Askari Mirza. Younger sons Olur (Alvor) Mirza, Anwar Mirza, Borbul Mirza and Farrukh Mirza died before their father when they were children. He experienced all the heat and cold of fate before he was twenty years old. Sometimes he appears before us in the form of an invisible prince, sometimes as a great and powerful king with a huge kingdom, sometimes as a defeated soldier, sometimes as a victorious general [1].

Although the Babur Empire was somewhat different from the feudal states that existed in the Muslim East of Central Asia in the Middle Ages, this empire existed for centuries in Turkestan and its surrounding states, a highly centralized, large military feudalism ruled by a single ruling king. was a state.

Such a huge kingdom can only be ruled by the means of a military system built on a powerful iron discipline. The main duty of the ruler was to regularly improve the army. The army is undergoing special inspections.

According to the Indian historian V.D. Mohajan, the armed forces in the Babur state were mainly divided into five categories, which consisted of cavalry, fighting elephant cavalry, infantry, artillery and archers, as well as many It was accompanied by a small number of naval and river fleet troops.

Each commander, even the military commanders of the vassal states, were given special titles and rights, and according to their position, they were paid a salary from the royal treasury or allocated land. Each commander has his own army, in which he must establish strong discipline, fill the ranks of the army, conduct military exercises with the soldiers, provide weapons, clothing and food for the army. - preparation of food reserves is entrusted to the army chief. As evidenced in the book "Aini Akbari" by Abulfazl, one of the skilled sarkadas of Akbar Shah's reign, one of the most accomplished scholars of his time, the cavalry army was divided into the following types according to the level of subordination to the kingdom.

1. "Ahadi" Navkars. Navkars belonging to this group were considered to belong to the highest category and acted only on the basis of a special decree of the king. They are commanded by a military official with the rank of "Devonbeki" 179 Scientific - information journal Armored shield - 6 (18) / 2022 or "Bakhshi", and recruits for this army were recruited for military service on behalf of the king. Ahadi navkars are well paid. If an ordinary cavalry soldier was paid 12-15 rupees, a soldier in the ahadi navkars was paid 500 rupees. The number of Ahadi sailors is about 7-8 thousand, and during the time of Akbar Shah, their number increased to 12 thousand people.

2. "Barvardi" workers. This type of Navkars consisted of the most skilled soldiers, who did not have their own horses. They were mainly used as armed police in domestic law enforcement.

3. "Komaki" navkars. The workers of this category are kept in reserve and sent to the places where they are needed in the process.

4. "Domestic" workers. This type of army formed the main base of the regular army in action. These types of sailors were attached to commanders who did not have their own army, and their horses were also marked with a special stamp.

In this category of soldiers, the title of king was at the disposal of the generals. This type of Navkars was very numerous, and during the reign of Akbar Shah, its number was 25 thousand, and during the reign of Jahangir and Shah Jahan, this number reached 300 thousand. If we add the Ahadi army at the disposal of the king, the internal army of the independent commanders, the army at the disposal of the governors of the regions and the army of the vassal states, the total amount of the army belonging to the kingdom reached 440,000 people. Cavalry made up the best part of the internal soldiers, and they were also classified according to the quality and quantity of

their horses. Among them, the "Boronghir" category received horses, weapons and clothes from the government. Soldiers belonging to the "Silador" group consisted of those who came to military service with their own horses and weapons.

5. Cavalry. Cavalry was the best part of the Babur army. Cavalry consists of the following units:

a) Borongir. The cavalry of Borongir received horses, weapons and clothes from the government.

b) Silador. Silador sailors consisted of those who came with their own horses and weapons.

Cavalry is divided into categories based on the quality of their horses. In the army of the Baburs, there were more Turkic and Chapikir greyhound horses. In addition, names classified as Arabic, Persian, muzanna, yabu and jangla were also used.

6. Foot soldiers. In the course of the battle, foot soldiers were also used effectively. They, in turn, are divided into riflemen and swordsmen. They also skillfully used bows, arrows and spears. In addition to soldiers, servants and water carriers were involved in the battle, and they did the preparation work, such as horse breeding and tent making. During the reign of Akbar Shah, foot soldiers became important in battle. They are divided into two categories: swordsmen and swordsmen.

7. War elephants. War elephants had a special position in the armies of the Baburs. Elephants are divided into seven different categories according to their quality and their owner's fighting skills. At the time of Akbar Shah, about a thousand war elephants were kept, and their number reached 50 thousand across the country. Elephants were used not only for fighting, but also for carrying goods.

8. Artillery. Baburshah entered India with powerful artillery. Akbar Shah further improved this type of army. During the reign of Akbar Shah, huge cannons were made, as well as small cannons that could be mounted on an elephant or a camel and carried.

One of the most remarkable features of the Babur army is its system of military officials. According to L.P. Sharma's historical sources, military officials were divided into ten different categories according to their position, and they were given salaries and rights accordingly. The lowest position official is given the right to command ten navkars 180 Scientific - information magazine Zirhli kalkan - 6 (18) / 2022 (ten head), and the highest official has the right to command an army of 12 thousand people has been

In addition, only princes of royal blood were allowed to lead an army of 5,000 to 4,000 soldiers. In addition, pendulums are divided into 33 categories.

Shah Jahan was given the right to command 5,000 cavalry and 8,000 infantry during his reign.

During the reign of Jahangirshah and Shah Jahan, military commanders had the right to command an army of 8,000 men, and princes had the right to command an army of 4,000 men. A commander with up to 2,500 soldiers was given the title of "Amir", a commander with more than 2,500 troops was given the title of "Amiri Azam", and commanders of a higher position were given the title of "Khoni Jahon". The highest military rank is "Khoni Khanon". Only the king dealt with the issue of salary and promotion of military officials. They were paid a salary or special land was allocated from the treasury. A military official also paid his servants at the expense of the state.

The main and most powerful part of the royal army was kept in the capital, and this army was moved only when the king himself rode. The rest of the army was kept in the areas of military importance, that is, in border areas where danger could come. A regular army was kept on the Kabul-Peshawar route, commanded by experienced and loyal generals. The most reliable means of protection from the enemy were fortresses, where many weapons and food stocks were stored [2].

Khumayun started to use new administration systems. He begins this work by dividing the courtiers into three parts and appoints a chief in charge of each part.

Those in the first parts call people of the state, that is, people of the state. These include army chiefs and toras, high-ranking people. The leaders of this group determined the military, the salaries of the palace guards, and appointed the total number of palace servants.

The second group is called people of happiness. It includes judges, clerics and sheikhs.

The third group is called people of desire. It included singers, poets, and cheerful, cheerful young people who enjoyed Humayun's time.

The state was governed by four courts.

It was called Charunsur, ex: fire (otashi), water (obi), earth (hoki) and air (hawai). The court of fire was engaged in military affairs. The court of air dealt with the palace economy, while the court of water was busy with irrigation, sweets and wine. The land court was engaged in tax collection, land administration and various constructions [3].

In conclusion, the life path of Baburshah and princes, their incomparable creative work, reforms in state administration, and universal ideas aroused great interest in the hearts of their compatriots. Currently, for several years, the services of our ancestors in the development of world military art have been studied in our country. Of course, as there is no future without history, if the military art of our ancestors is not studied, it will be difficult for us to achieve

success in modern military operations in the future. In today's dangerous world, I believe that it is our important task to study the military heritage left by our ancestors in depth and carefully.

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